

1 **p53 Y234C activates Dux homeobox factors DuxAP9 and DuxAP10 and Mbd3l2.**

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7 Dux homeobox factors are related to induction of ECT2 as a universal production of transformation in solid
8 tumors. A major component transcriptional property of the Dux family homeobox factors (including
9 DUXAP9) is control expression of MBD3L2 and related molecules. BRWD1, an imprinting system
10 regulatory factor could control expression of MBD3L2 demonstrating genetic perturbation or mutation of
11 BRWD1 was sufficient to activate MBD3L2 and that modulation of an Xist-associated imprinting factor
12 could drive production of a transformation intermediate.

13 Here we present further evidence demonstrating that Xist and the Xist-associated imprinting system, a
14 large but incompetent defined entity, could drive transformation. Xist and the associated imprinting system
15 were partially sufficient to support oncogenesis in human cells and tissues *in vitro*.

16 Xist induction was further associated with DUXAP homeobox factor induction in the context of
17 transformation, because specific induction of Xist following expression of a p53 point mutant in human
18 cells (Y234C) resulted in activation of DuxAP9 and DuxAP10, homeobox factors that we separately show
19 control transcription of the major solid tumor protein ECT2.
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